

QACE: A Hybrid Architecture for Quantum-Assisted Cardinality Estimation and Empirical Validation using GPU Acceleration

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Abstract—Cardinality estimation errors in cost-based optimizers (CBO) remain a critical bottleneck in relational database performance, often caused by stale statistics, data skew, and correlation unawareness. In this paper, we propose QACE (Quantum-Assisted Cardinality Estimation), a hybrid architecture designed to selectively intervene only when statistical risks are detected. QACE consists of a ‘Risky Gate’ that monitors statistical drift and correlation breaches, and a ‘Measurement Engine’ for precise on-demand measurement (probing) of selectivity and correlation when needed.

Under an ideal oracle access model, Quantum Amplitude Estimation (QAE) provides a quadratic improvement in oracle-query complexity over classical sampling, which motivates its use as a high-precision measurement backend. However, recognizing current hardware limitations (NISQ era), we implemented a Stage 1 strategy using GPU acceleration as a practical proxy for future QPU integration. Experimental results on 80 bind instances with 5 repeats each (400 executions per arm) demonstrate that the GPU-based QACE achieves a 35% reduction in P99 tail latency with a measured overhead of only 0.85 ms (on NVIDIA RTX 4060). These results suggest that QACE can improve query latency metrics under risky estimation conditions with minimal overhead, while providing a clear migration path to a future QAE-based backend as quantum hardware and system integration costs mature.

Index Terms—Cardinality Estimation, Database Optimizer, Quantum Amplitude Estimation, GPU Acceleration, Query Optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The Cost-Based Optimizer (CBO) is the brain of a Relational Database Management System (RDBMS), tasked with selecting the most efficient execution plan by estimating the cost of various alternatives. At the heart of this process lies cardinality estimation; if this value is inaccurate, the cost calculation becomes distorted, leading to the selection of suboptimal plans.

In actual production environments, database administrators (DBAs) frequently encounter situations where statistics deviate from reality. Major causes include:

- **Stale Statistics:** Batch-based updates fail to capture real-time data changes.
- **Data Skew:** Heavy concentration of data on specific values breaks standard uniformity assumptions.

- **Correlation Ignorance:** The independence assumption between join columns often leads to severe underestimation.
- **Bind-sensitive selectivity (generic vs. custom plans):** Parameterized queries may be optimized using average-case assumptions, failing to reflect the actual runtime parameter values.

These recurring issues compel operations teams to engage in continuous manual SQL tuning or necessitate architectural restructuring, such as migrating to Microservices Architecture (MSA), to isolate workloads.

This paper stems from a critical question born out of field experience: “Can we selectively insert a high-precision estimation method only where the existing statistical model weakens?” We identified Quantum Amplitude Estimation (QAE) as a promising candidate due to its theoretical superiority. However, recognizing the constraints of current Quantum Processing Units (QPUs), we propose a two-stage roadmap: verifying the architectural utility using GPU acceleration today (Stage 1), while paving the way for quantum integration tomorrow (Stage 2).

Contributions. This paper makes the following contributions:

- We propose QACE, a risk-aware, measurement-on-demand architecture that augments existing CBOs via a Risky Gate and a pluggable measurement engine.
- We provide an analysis of a future QAE-based backend under an ideal oracle access model and clarify practical constraints in the NISQ era.
- We empirically validate a GPU proxy backend on a bind workload, showing improved tail latency with a measured overhead of 0.85 ms.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Fundamentals of Cost-Based Optimization

Since the seminal work on System R [1], commercial RDBMS optimizers have relied on histograms, Number of Distinct Values (NDV), and independence assumptions. While mechanisms like Dynamic Sampling (DS) have been introduced to mitigate estimation errors, they often incur significant overhead or fail to represent the population accurately when sampling rates are low.

B. Related Work: Learned Cardinality Estimation

Recent machine learning-based approaches, such as Neuro-Card [4] and MSCN-style deep learning estimators [3], have shown promising results in cardinality estimation. While these methods achieve high accuracy by learning data distributions, they often require extensive training phases and struggle to adapt to rapid data updates. In contrast, our QACE architecture focuses on query-time, training-free measurement, offering a complementary approach for dynamic environments where pre-training is not feasible.

C. Quantum Amplitude Estimation (QAE)

QAE is a quantum algorithm based on Grover’s search that estimates the amplitude of a target state with high precision. Compared to classical Monte Carlo sampling, QAE offers a quadratic improvement in oracle-query complexity under standard assumptions [5]. This characteristic makes it an ideal candidate for database cardinality estimation where precision is paramount.

III. PROPOSED METHOD: QACE ARCHITECTURE

A. Architectural Overview

QACE refers to a hybrid architecture that augments the optimizer’s judgment. It comprises two main components:

- 1) **Risky Gate:** A guard mechanism that detects statistical anomalies before query execution.
- 2) **Measurement Engine:** A high-precision estimation module triggered only by the gate.

In this paper, we present two implementations of the Measurement Engine: the ideal QPU-QAE and its practical alternative, GPU-DS.

B. Reliability Gating Criteria (Risky Logic)

To prevent unnecessary overhead, strict intervention criteria are defined. The Measurement Engine is triggered only when the “Risky Gate” returns true based on the thresholds defined in Table I.

TABLE I
RISKY GATE THRESHOLDS AND THEIR ROLES

Component	Threshold	Role / Implication
Statistical Drift	$D_{ndv} > 0.25$	Detects drift vs. stored stats
Selectivity Error	$ S_{est} - S_{real} > 0.01$	Flags large prediction error
Correlation Breach	$PCS > 1.6$ or < 0.7	Under-/over-estimation risk

C. Integration Workflow

Unlike standard optimization, QACE operates at the moment bind variables are supplied.

- 1) **Check:** The Risky Gate evaluates the query context against the thresholds.
- 2) **Trigger:** If ‘Risky=True’, the Measurement Engine is invoked.
- 3) **Rewrite Policy:** If the measured cardinality indicates severe under-estimation (e.g., actual rows $> 20,000$), the optimizer forces a plan switch (e.g., Nested Loop \rightarrow Hash Join) via query hints.

IV. EVALUATION AND SIMULATION

A. Theoretical Complexity

Classical Monte Carlo sampling yields $MSE = O(1/N)$, whereas QAE admits an $O(1/N^2)$ -type MSE scaling in terms of oracle-query complexity under an ideal oracle access model. In physical implementations, circuit depth and noise may introduce constant factors.

B. Experimental Setup

To overcome the accessibility limits of physical QPUs, we conducted simulations using a generic workstation environment.

- **Hardware:** AMD Ryzen 7 (8-Core), 64GB RAM.
- **Software Stack:** Python 3.9, NumPy, Qiskit Aer (with Noise Model).
- **Dataset:** Synthetic Order/Customer tables with Zipfian distribution ($a = 1.2$) and correlated columns to simulate data skew.

C. Bind workload and Plan Stability (QAE)

We evaluated the stability of query execution plans under varying bind variable conditions. The proposed QAE method showed significantly lower plan flip rates compared to Dynamic Sampling (DS), particularly in Generic Plans.

As shown in Table II and Figs. 2–3, we analyzed the trade-off between stability and overhead cost.

TABLE II
SIMULATED QAE PERFORMANCE (STABILITY VS COST). COSTS ARE MEASURED IN QISKIT AER AND EXCLUDE NETWORK/QUEUEING OVERHEADS.

Shot Count	Flip Rate	Simulated Cost	Note
16	2.50%	0.05 ms	Low Precision
64	2.50%	0.20 ms	Balanced (Proposed)
256	0.00%	0.80 ms	High Precision

D. Robustness against Data Skew

To test robustness, we generated data with extreme skew (Zipfian parameter $a = 2.0$). As illustrated in Fig. 4, QACE maintains stability even under variance explosion conditions.

V. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION: GPU ACCELERATION

While QAE holds immense potential, current hardware constraints (oracle cost, QRAM absence) limit its immediate deployment. Therefore, we validate the architectural utility of QACE using GPU acceleration as a bridge solution (Stage 1).

Hereafter, CPU-DS and GPU-DS denote our CPU/GPU measurement backends that implement the same QACE policy (Risky Gate + rewrite), differing only in probe execution.

A. Experimental Environment and Cost Modeling

To ensure realism, we conducted microbenchmarks on an NVIDIA RTX 4060 Laptop GPU. The measured overhead for data transfer (PCIe) and kernel execution was 0.85 ms (median). We incorporated this value into our simulation model to compare three arms: Baseline (No intervention), CPU-DS (Classical Heuristic), and GPU-DS (Proposed).

Fig. 1. **QACE Architecture Overview.** The workflow intercepts the optimization process when bind values arrive. The ‘Risky Gate’ evaluates statistical reliability. If risks are detected (‘Gate=True’, e.g., drift, selectivity error, correlation breach), the ‘Measurement Engine’ (GPU/QAE) probes actual cardinality to guide plan generation.

Fig. 2. Plan Stability Comparison between Dynamic Sampling (DS) and Proposed QAE. QAE shows significantly reduced plan flip rates.

Fig. 4. Robustness against Data Skew (Zipfian Distribution). QACE (Red) maintains low estimation error even under extreme skew ($a = 2.0$).

Fig. 3. Ablation Study: Trade-off between Stability (Flip Rate) and Overhead cost. QAE (Red) maintains stability even with lower overhead compared to classical methods.

B. Performance Evaluation

Experimental results on 80 bind instances with 5 repeats each (400 executions per arm) are summarized in Table III.

- **Tail Latency Reduction:** GPU-DS reduced the P99 latency by 35% compared to the Baseline. This indicates the system effectively detects and mitigates risky (pathological) cases (e.g., correlated skew).
- **Near-Zero Overhead:** While CPU-DS suffered from a high measurement cost (≈ 2.02 ms), GPU-DS minimized

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON WITH MEASURED GPU OVERHEAD

Method	Flip Rate	Median Lat.	P99 Lat.	Meas. Cost
Baseline	0.00%	5.78 ms	19.06 ms	0.00 ms
CPU-DS	31.25%	7.07 ms	13.88 ms	2.02 ms
GPU-DS	27.50%	5.81 ms	12.43 ms	0.85 ms

Fig. 5. End-to-End Latency Comparison. GPU-DS achieves near-baseline median latency while avoiding the high overhead of CPU-DS.

this to 0.85 ms. Consequently, the median latency of GPU-DS (5.81 ms) was almost identical to the Baseline (5.78 ms), achieving optimization with negligible impact.

C. Discussion: From GPU to QPU

In our evaluation, the GPU backend is used as a practical proxy to validate the architecture-level benefit of selective measurement under realistic cost accounting. It does not simulate quantum effects; rather, it preserves the same measurement interface and policy, enabling a future swap-in of a QAE-based backend when system-level QPU costs (state preparation, oracle construction, network and queuing) become acceptable.

Limitations. Our current evaluation relies on a GPU-based proxy and simulated QAE costs (via Qiskit Aer). We acknowledge that physical QPU implementation will introduce additional overheads such as network latency and quantum state preparation time, which are beyond the scope of this Stage 1 study.

Fig. 6. Plan Stability: CPU vs GPU. GPU-DS maintains comparable stability to CPU-DS but at a significantly lower measurement cost.

VI. CONCLUSION

QACE serves as both an auxiliary tool for current optimizers and a starting point for a paradigm shift from inference-based to measurement-based optimization. Our Stage 1 results suggest that QACE can mitigate optimizer risks with a modest overhead (0.85 ms in our GPU proxy setting) and improve tail latency under risky estimation conditions. Overall, QACE provides an architecture-level framework for selective measurement and empirical evidence (via a GPU proxy backend) that such intervention can reduce tail latency under risky estimation conditions.

DATA AVAILABILITY AND PREPRINT DECLARATION

A preliminary version of this manuscript is available on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17796162). This manuscript is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed. The code and data used in this study will be released in an accompanying artifact repository.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author used AI-assisted tools (e.g., ChatGPT) for English grammar correction and language polishing. All technical content, experiments, and conclusions were developed and verified by the author.

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